
COMPOSITE CONFIGURATION OPTIMIZATION BY METAHEURISTIC ALGORITHM

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Abstract. *This document present the use of optimization method to obtain the best composite configuration to an specific geometry and load. And are presented some simple analysis with knowing cases. The Tensile Plate optimization found a configuration very close of the knowing configuration with an error of 0,36% at run 1 and 3,41% at run 2. The Twisted Tube optimization found a configuration with an error of 0,50% at run 1 and 0,00% at run 2. And the natural frequency maximization of the tube in an error of 0,00%.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite the bigger utilization of composites at the industry, and the new possibilities created by the technological advance of fabrication, the application of the optimization methods to define the fiber orientation and the stacking sequence, has been promissory. The use of optimizations methods becomes interesting, with the objective of evaluating and selecting the best configuration for a given type of loading, and specific geometry.

In this work there is the application of the Particle Swarm Optimization Method (PSO) to define the fiber orientation of the composite materials. The study consists on an analysis of possibilities to future uses. There are two cases implemented, and solved, each one, by two methods. At the results of this paper there is a comparations an feasibility analysis of this procedures, and suggestions to future studies.

2. BIBLIOGRAPHIC REVIEW

Santana, Gomes and Awruch [1], performed the optimization of a composite material plate in order to minimize the first natural frequency. The optimization variables was the control point of a spline used to determine the fiber angle of each element of the plate, solved by Finite Elements of Plate.

Omkar, Senthinath and Khandelwal [2] realized the optimization of a composite structure with multiple objective function of weight and cost minimization. The optimization variables are number of plies, thickness and angle of align of each ply. The failure criterium was obtained with the classical lamination theory.

This commented papers shows two different approaches to solve the structural problem: Finite Element Method and Analytical Method. The second one, despite the easily and fast solve is restrict to some simply cases. To complex geometries Finite Element Methods become the unique possible solution.

2.1. Composite Material

According to Kaw [3], the composite is that composed by at least two constituents, matrix and reinforcement, the second usually at fiber form, arranged in plies, as show in Fig. 1. Because the two phases, it is an anisotropic material.

Figure 1 – Nomenclature of a composite material.

Typically the fiber has a specific align at each ply.

To the evaluation of the structural response of the composite is used the Tsai-Wu failure criterium (FC_{TW}), throw the Eq. (1).

$$FC_{TW} = H_1\sigma_1 + H_2\sigma_2 + H_6\tau_{12} + H_{11}\sigma_1^2 + H_{22}\sigma_2^2 + H_{66}\tau_{12}^2 + 2H_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 < 1 \quad (1)$$

Where H_1 , H_2 , H_6 , H_{11} , H_{22} , H_{66} and H_{12} are parameters of the Tsai-Wu Failure Criterium defined by Kaw [3]. And σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} are the local stress of the ply, defined by the ply orientation.

2.2. Optimization Method

The optimization problem can be defined by Belegundo and Chandrupatla [4] with the Eq. (2).

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize } f_i(\mathbf{x}) \\ \text{s. t. } & \begin{cases} g_j(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0 \\ h_k(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \\ \mathbf{x}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_{\max} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where f_i are the Objective Functions, \mathbf{x} are the optimization parameters, g_j are the inequality constrains, h_k are the equality constrains and \mathbf{x}_{\min} and \mathbf{x}_{\max} are respectively the maximum and minimum values to the optimization parameters.

To solve them, several methods ca be applied. Because the non linear and constrained characteristic, is need to be converted into a nom constrained problem by the Penalty Function [5] in the Eq. (3).

$$pf(\mathbf{x}) = f(\mathbf{x}) + \sum_{j=1}^n \max[0; g_j(\mathbf{x})]^2 + \sum_{k=1}^n h_k(\mathbf{x})^2 \quad (3)$$

The Eq. (3) acts penalizing the objective function when some of the constrains are violated.

To solve the problem, the Swarm Optimization Method, developed by Kennedy and Eberhart [6], are elected. The method consists on the variables update by three parameters: inertia, cognitive (memory) and social parameters of a group of particles random initialized. Following the equations:

$$\mathbf{v}^{t+1} = w^t \cdot \mathbf{v}^t + r_1 \cdot c_1 \cdot (\mathbf{x}_{pbest} - \mathbf{x}^t) + r_2 \cdot c_2 \cdot (\mathbf{x}_{gbest} - \mathbf{x}^t) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{x}^{t+1} = \mathbf{x}^t + \mathbf{v}^{t+1} \quad (5)$$

Where \mathbf{v}^t are the vector of velocities of the particles, w^t is the inertia parameters, r_1 and r_2 are two random values between 0 and 1. c_1 are the cognitive parameter, and c_2 are the social parameters (used 2 for both of then at this work).

The vectors \mathbf{x}_{pbest} and \mathbf{x}_{gbest} are the optimization variables values of the best fit of the Objective Function, respectively to each particle and to all particles. That means \mathbf{x}_{pbest} are the position of best fit found by each particle (each particle has its values) and \mathbf{x}_{gbest} are the position of best fit of all particles (same values to all particles).

Two modifications of the original method are implemented at this work. The first one is, according Zheng [7], the inertia parameter (w^t), increasing linearly with the iterations at the Eq. (6):

$$w^t = w_{\min} + \frac{(w_{\max} - w_{\min}) \cdot t}{t_{\max}} \quad (6)$$

Where $w_{\max} = 0.9$ and $w_{\min} = 0.1$.

And according Esposito and Gomes [8] the vector \mathbf{x}_{gbest} of the optimization variables global best solution updates asynchronously. It means \mathbf{x}_{gbest} founded at the current iterations be available to updates \mathbf{v}^t and \mathbf{x}^t of the remaining particles of the iteration.

This two adaptations, according the respective authors, are able to facilitate the convergency and increase the quality of the final result.

3. METHOD

In this work there is the application of the Particle Swarm Optimization in some cases further commented. All this cases are solved by the Particle Swarm Optimization with Finite Elements Method (FEM) from Ansys. As detailed at Fig. 2.

1. Random initialization of \mathbf{x} with values between \mathbf{x}_{\min} and \mathbf{x}_{\max} for all particles;
2. Initialization of velocities vector \mathbf{v} with zeros, for all particles;
3. Loop throw iterations t:
 - 3.1. Loop throw particles j:
 - 3.1.1. Solve the problem of FEM;
 - 3.1.2. Calculate the Objective Function and the Penalty Function with Eq. (3);
 - 3.1.3. If $pf(\mathbf{x})$ smaller than $pf(\mathbf{x}_{pbest})$ update \mathbf{x}_{pbest} ;
 - 3.1.4. If $pf(\mathbf{x})$ smaller than $pf(\mathbf{x}_{gbest})$ update \mathbf{x}_{gbest} ;
 - 3.1.5. Update the optimization parameters of the particle j with the Eq. (4) and Eq. (5);
4. Verify the convergency.

Figure 2 – Pseudo code of the optimization of composite.

There are 15 particles and the stop criteria are: the limit of 100 iteration (Run 1 of each case) or 10 consecutives iterations without \mathbf{x}_{gbest} update (Run 2 of each case).

The FEM analysis are made at Ansys Workbench and the optimization algorithm implemented in python as a script of Ansys workbench. The composite chosen are the unidirectional glass fiber.

3.1. Case A: Tensile Plate

Consists on a 0.2 m by 0.1 m plate with four plies of 0.0002 m each one. It is fixed at one of the ends and tensile with 10 000 N at the other one. The Fig. 3 shows the configuration.

Figure 3 – The Plate with indications of constraint and load to the FEM model.

To correct express the problem, then are propose the Eq. (7):

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize } f(\mathbf{x}) = \varepsilon_{x_{\max}} \\ \text{s. t. } & \begin{cases} g_i(\mathbf{x}) = FC_{TW_i} - 1 < 0 & \text{with } i = 1 \dots 4 \\ \mathbf{x}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_{\max} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Where $\varepsilon_{x_{\max}}$ is the maximum global strain of the composite, at direction x (load direction) and with all components of the vector \mathbf{x}_{\min} equals to -90° and the components of \mathbf{x}_{\max} equals to 90° .

3.2. Case B: Twisted Tube

It is a 0.05 m of external diameter, and 0.2 m of length with a torsion load of 100 Nm. It is show at Fig. 4.

Figure 4 – The Tube with indications of constraint and load to the FEM model.

The problem can be defined with the Eq. (8):

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize } f(\mathbf{x}) = \gamma_{xy_{\max}} \\ \text{s. t. } & g_i(\mathbf{x}) = FC_{TW_i} - 1 < 0 \quad \text{with } i = 1 \dots 4 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Where $\gamma_{xy_{\max}}$ is the maximum global shear of the composite and to \mathbf{x}_{\min} components with 0° and \mathbf{x}_{\max} components 180° , considering 90° as the same direction of the tube's axe.

3.3. Case C: Natural Frequency of Plate

It is a 0.2 m by 0.1 m plate with four plies of 0.0002 m each one. It is fixed at one of the ends The Fig. 5 shows it.

Figure 5 – The Plate with indications of constraint to the FEM model.

The problem is defined at Eq. (9).

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{maximize } f(\mathbf{x}) = f_1 \\ & \text{s. t. } \{ \mathbf{x}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_{\max} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Where f_1 is the first natural frequency.

The components of \mathbf{x}_{\min} are equals to -90° and the components of \mathbf{x}_{\max} equals to 90° . The convergency criterium was the limit of 100 iterations.

4. RESULTS

The results at each studied case, with the Objective Function historic is commented at each subtitle:

4.1. Case A: Tensile Plate

The parameters and variables values of the analysis results are at Tab. 1 and the Objective Function historic at Fig. 6. The final value of Objective Function represents an error of the know solution of 0,36% at Run 1 with just convergence criterium of 100 iterations. Because of fast convergence it was modified with the convergence criterium of 10 consecutives iterations without $\mathbf{x}_{\text{gbest}}$ update at Run 2, with a convergence error of 3.41%. At Run 2 occurred just 42 iterations until the convergence criterium.

Table 1: Parameters values of the Tensile Plate optimization.

Parameter	0/0/0/0 laminate	Run 1	Run 2
Ply 1 angel	0°	-2,05°	4,97°
Ply 2 angel	0°	0,16°	-2,66°
Ply 3 angel	0°	-2,62°	-7,30°
Ply 4 angel	0°	1,40°	3,28°
Ply 1 failure criterium	0,15192	0,16320	0,2081
Ply 2 failure criterium	0,15192	0,15326	0,15885
Ply 3 failure criterium	0,15192	0,16212	0,22589
Ply 4 failure criterium	0,15192	0,16026	0,15566
Maximun strain at X axe	0,00265 m/m	0,00266 m/m	0,00274 m/m

Figure 6 –Objective Function Historic of the Tensile Plate.

4.2. Case B: Twisted Tube

The parameters values of the results are at Tab. 2 and the Objective Function historic at Fig. 7.

Table 2: Parameters values of the Twisted Tube optimization.

Parameter	45/-45/45/-45 laminate	45/-45/-45/45 laminate	-45/45/45/-45 laminate	Run 1	Run 2
Ply 1 angel	45°	45°	-45°	41,98°	45,08°
Ply 2 angel	-45°	-45°	45°	133,95°	134,93°
Ply 3 angel	45°	-45°	45°	132,63°	134,87°
Ply 4 angel	-45°	45°	-45°	46,70°	45,16°
Ply 1 failure criteriun	0,2085	0,38871	0,12421	0,3917	0,3887
Ply 2 failure criteriun	0,16426	0,11577	0,35999	0,1162	0,1158
Ply 3 failure criteriun	0,36323	0,11229	0,35264	0,1144	0,1123
Ply 4 failure criteriun	0,16042	0,36017	0,11412	0,3549	0,3600
Maximun deformation	0,000731 m	0,000594 m	0,000594 m	0,000597 m	0,000594 m

Figure 7 –Objective Function Historic of the Twisted Tube.

There is a error of 0,50% of error at the result of the optimization, in comparation of the knowing laminate of 45/-45/-45/45. And with a total of 73 iterations at the Run 2, it was found an insignificant error. That means an excellent convergency results.

4.3. Case C: Natural Frequency of Plate

At the Tab. 3 there is the parameters of the result configurations and at Fig. 8. This analysis results in an insignificant error.

Table 3: Parameters values of the Twisted Tube optimization.

Parameter	0/0/0 laminate	Run 1
Ply 1 angel	0°	0,03°
Ply 2 angel	0°	-0,01°
Ply 3 angel	0°	-0,00°
Ply 4 angel	0°	0,00°
First Natural Frequency	16,25 Hz	16,25 Hz

Figure 8 –Objective Function Historic of the Natural Frequency maximization of plate.

5. CONCLUSION

The results shows the possibility of implementation of optimization algorithm to obtain the best composite configuration to an specific load and geometry case. It enables found configurations of the composite, reducing a manual search, and ensuring the best solution.

The computational cost is an obstacle, because the need of the high FEM evaluating quantities.

In a general way the method describe at this paper can be a usefully at some complex geometries and loads, founding a ideally composite configuration, but with an elevated computational cost.

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